

four RRS upland experimental sites (Table 1).

In 1979 the experiments were conducted separately for each variety in randomized, treated and untreated paired plots replicated six times. Seeds were drilled at 80 kg/ha with 20 cm between rows. In 1980 the experiments were carried out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Four or five seeds were sown in hills spaced 20 × 15 cm. Plot size was 6 × 2 m, and treated plots received 4 sprayings of benomyl between tillering and dough stages at 0.33 kg ai/ha per spray. About 20 randomly chosen fertile tillers per plot were assessed for infection.

Percentages of the visible area of the leaf lamina infected, from the flag leaf and from three (1979) and two (1980) successive leaves for each tiller selected were averaged for each plot at dough stage in 1979, and at boot and dough stages in 1980. Infection rates between boot and dough stages were calculated for the 1980 experiments.

The varieties did not significantly differ in leaf area infected (Table 1). This

Table 2. *Rhynchosporium oryzae* infection rates between boot and dough stages in 2 rice varieties in 1980 in Sierra Leone^a

Experimental site	Treatment	Infection rate ^b	
		ROK16	PN623-3
Masorie-NP	Benomyl	0.044	0.046
	Untreated	0.043	0.057
Sendugu-NP	Benomyl	0.016	0.003
	Untreated	0.041	0.026
Kenema-EP	Benomyl	0.012	0.029
	Untreated	0.029	0.039

^aNP = Northern Province, within 8 km from RRS; EP = Eastern Province, 360 km from RRS. ROK16 and PN623-3 have broad-droopy and narrow-erect leaves, respectively. LSD ($P = 0.05$) are 0.043 (Masorie), 0.043 (Sendugu), 0.030 (Kenema). Untreated plants were artificially inoculated at Masorie. ^bAfter Van der Plank.

observation was also true for the Masorie experiment in 1980 where plots which did not receive benomyl were artificially inoculated with *R. oryzae* conidia at maximum tillering stage. Symptoms from natural inoculum were rarely apparent before maximum tillering. Average leaf area infected in untreated plots was relatively low — between 0.2 and 5.9% for ROK16 and 0.3 and 7% for PN623-3.

Average infection was lowest in the flag leaves and increased progressively on the leaves below. The differences in infec-

tion rates were not significant ($P = 0.05$) (Table 2). Benomyl significantly reduced infection and, except for one instance, slowed the infection rate. In plots where enough disease developed to cause loss, average losses for both years were 15.3% for ROK16 and 12.6% for PN623-3. Correlation coefficients (r) between percent leaf area infected and yield for plots were significant ($P = 0.05$) only when r was calculated separately for each variety at each site for a given year. □

Rice tungro virus complex in tungro-resistant IR varieties

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Tungro disease is associated with a virus complex composed of small bacilliform and isometric virus particles recently described as rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). Diseased plants exhibited severe symptoms when infected with both particles; mild symptoms with RTBV alone; and are almost symptomless with RTSV alone.

The presence of the RTV complex on IR36, IR42, IR50, IR54, and IR56, bred as tungro-resistant varieties, was determined by the latex agglutination test using antisera to RTBV and RTSV, and the virus recovery test using the vector insect *Nephotettix virescens*. Tungro-infected plants were obtained by inoculating 6-day-old seedlings with 1 insect per seedling in test tubes for 24 hours.

The latex agglutination test involved

A light micrograph shows clumping of latex particles indicating the presence of virus (right). No clumping (left) indicates absence of virus.

mixing equal volumes of a very small amount of plant sap and a suspension of latex particles (Difco Bacto Latex 0.81) treated with an antiserum. The mixture was then agitated vigorously for 5–10

min. The presence of the virus in the plant sap was indicated by the clumping or agglutination of the latex particles as observed under the light microscope (see figure).

About 57, 42, and 27% of IR42, IR56, and IR36 plants sampled showed RTBV and RTSV. The other sampled plants showed RTBV only. However, all IR50 and IR54 plants sampled reacted to RTBV only. All plants of the susceptible check TN1 reacted to both RTBV and RTSV. No variety reacted to the presence of RTSV only (Table 1).

Attempts to recover the virus from the infected plants were made using *N. virescens*. Recovery was successful from plants infected with RTBV and RTSV. In the recovery tests involving 52 plants infected with RTBV alone, 1,408 seedlings were inoculated with 326 insects that were given 4 days acquisition time on the plants. No positive transmission was obtained regardless of variety (Table 2).

This is the first finding that shows a connection between the presence of RTBV alone in varieties with a high level of resistance to the vector, and with fairly low percentage of tungro infection. Although infected, these plants will not serve as virus source for the spread of the disease. □

Table 1. Presence of RTV complex on 5 IR varieties as detected by the latex agglutination test.

Variety	Reaction to		Plants tested (no.)	Plants (no.) that reacted to the presence of		
	GLH ^a	RTV ^b		RTBV + RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
IR36	MR	S	15	4	11	0
IR42	MR	S	14	8	6	0
IR50	R	I	13	0	13	0
IR54	R	I	15	0	15	0
IR56	R to MR ^c	S	12	5	7	0
TN1	S	S	13	13	0	0

^a Data from IRRI Entomology Department. ^bGreenhouse mass-screening results, IRRI Plant Pathology Department: 0 = 30% infection, resistant (R); 31-60%, intermediate (I); 61-100%, susceptible (S). ^c Reaction varies from resistant (R) to moderately resistant (MR).

Table 2. Virus recovery from plants containing both RTBV and RTSV or RTBV alone using the vector insect *N. virescens*.

Variety	RTBV and RTSV ^a			RTBV alone ^c	
	Plants tested ^b (no.)	Insects tested (no.)	Infective insects (no.)	Plants tested (no.)	Insects tested (no.)
IR36	4	34	24	11	97
IR4	8	79	66	6	56
IR50	—	—	—	13	55
IR54	—	—	—	15	14
IR5	5	43	27	7	44
TN	113	108	71	—	—

^a A dash indicates no recovery test conducted because no plant reacted to the presence of the virus.

^b Virus was recovered from all plants tested. ^c No plant or insect tested yielded the virus.

Pest management and control INSECTS

Rice yield loss caused by leaffolder damage at tillering stage

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Yield loss caused by leaffolder infestation at tillering stage was studied in the greenhouse by artificially infesting 55-day-old IR20 plants with 0, 1, 2, or 3 larvae/tiller. Each 30-cm pot had 5 tillers at infestation. The experiment was replicated 6 times.

The number of leaves damaged and total leaves in each infested tiller was recorded when larvae pupated. Percent of leaves damaged was calculated. Grains from individual tillers were collected at maturity, percentage of unfilled grains was calculated, and grain weight was estimated (see table).

Damage and yield in leaffolder-infested IR20^a

Larvae (no.) /tiller	Leaves damaged ^b (%)	Mean yield ^b (g/tiller)	Yield reduction (%)	Unfilled (%)
0		2.1 a		9.6
1	43.6 a	1.1 b	48.8	29.1
2	58.8 b	1.0 b	52.2	26.2
3	70.8 b	0.9 b	56.9	29.0

^a Mean of 30 tillers. ^b Means followed by common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

Leaf damage was significantly lower for plants infested with 1 larva/tiller, but the yield did not differ significantly among the treatments. Yield was reduced by 49 to 57% for all treatments and 26 to 29% of grains were unfilled.

The regression of grain yield on the percentage of leaves damaged, and

1. Regression of grain yield on percentage of leaves damaged by leaffolder. (n = 120)

